

LEVEL OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE COAST GUARD DAMAGE CONTROLMAN RATING COURSE AND TRAINEE ONBOARD PERFORMANCE TOWARD PROGRAM ENHANCEMENT

CG CDR Julio S Colarina III

Graduate School Department, Philippine Merchant Marine Academy, Manila, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12218524>

ABSTRACT

The study employed a quantitative descriptive approach to evaluate the effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course (DCRC) and its impact on trainee onboard Performance. A sample size of 150 trainees was chosen to ensure statistical power and precision, to detect meaningful differences or trends in the data. The methodology included surveys and performance assessments to gather comprehensive data on trainees' experiences and outcomes. The analysis process involved statistical techniques to identify significant patterns and relationships. Findings revealed a pressing need for improvements in hands-on experience with firefighting equipment and room simulations for practical exercises. Respondents expressed dissatisfaction with outdated technology and poorly maintained equipment in training facilities, underscoring the necessity for significant upgrades. The study also identified a significant positive relationship between the course's effectiveness and trainees' Performance in managing shipboard emergencies, highlighting the critical importance of clear course objectives, comprehensive content, proficient instructors, and high-quality materials and facilities. In conclusion, while the Damage Controlman Rating Course demonstrates effectiveness in several key areas, there is considerable room for improvement, particularly in upgrading training facilities and equipment. Recommendations include prioritizing comprehensive course enhancements, tailoring training to address variations in effectiveness, implementing continuous evaluation and feedback mechanisms, and fostering a culture of constant learning and improvement within the Coast Guard community. These recommendations aim to enhance the course's effectiveness further and ensure participants are well-prepared to handle shipboard emergencies effectively.

Keywords: *Damage Controlman Rating Course (DCRC), Trainee onboard performance, Course objectives, Course Contents, Instructor Capabilities, and Training Materials and Facilities.*

INTRODUCTION

The training and preparedness of Coast Guard personnel are critical for ensuring maritime safety and operational efficiency. Among the various training programs, the Coast Guard Damage Controlman Rating Course (DCRC) stands out as a vital component. This course is designed to equip Coast Guard members with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform damage control duties effectively. Its impact is directly observable in trainees' performance once onboard and undertaking real-world missions. The course's effectiveness not only influences individual Performance but also contributes significantly to the overall operational efficiency and safety of Coast Guard missions.

The Damage Controlman Rating Course encompasses a comprehensive curriculum that includes both theoretical and practical elements. Trainees are prepared to handle emergencies such as fire outbreaks and structural damages in harsh maritime environments. The evolving nature of marine threats and operational challenges necessitates continuously assessing and enhancing this course. Safety concerns are prevalent in damage control procedures on Coast Guard vessels, necessitating an examination of current practices to identify potential hazards and propose improvements to enhance overall crew and ship safety.

The importance of the DCR Course in Coast Guard personnel training is well-documented. Jackson (2018), Fernandes and Ribeiro (2017), Guard (2019), and Carmassi et al. (2020) have all highlighted their critical role. The course focuses on leadership, communication, teamwork, equipment maintenance, ship stability, chemical, biological, and radiological defence, and hazardous material management. It enhances situational awareness among sailors, enabling them to identify hazards, assess damage severity, and make informed decisions during crises. The course also emphasizes CBR defence and hazardous material management, ensuring trainees are proficient in these critical areas. Overall, the DCR Course is crucial for Coast Guard personnel to handle emergencies effectively and safeguard vessels and crew members.

Evaluating the training effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course is essential. It involves assessing whether the course adequately prepares individuals for real-world damage control situations and identifying areas for refinement better to meet the needs of trainees and operational demands. Additionally, the operational efficiency of damage control measures is vital, as streamlining and optimizing procedures ensures that the response to damage incidents is swift, well-coordinated, and minimally disruptive to overall Coast Guard operations.

Several studies have highlighted the importance of effective training programs in maritime and military contexts. For example, Alberto (2019) emphasized the necessity of experienced leadership in maintaining high operational standards. Similarly,

Cucharó (2022) found a correlation between age, experience, and professional advancement, underscoring the importance of continuous training and experience in maintaining operational readiness. These findings highlight the significance of experience and constant training in high-stakes environments like the Coast Guard.

Damage factors in Coast Guard vessels provide crucial insights into the multifaceted nature of challenges faced in the maritime industry and the pivotal role of the Coast Guard Damage Controlman Rating Course in addressing them. Romulo et al. (2019) explore damage factors such as wear and tear and corrosion, highlighting the importance of proactive measures taught in the course. Tolentino (2019) emphasizes the critical role of safety protocol adherence and ongoing training, while Silo (2019) underscores the financial implications of damage and the importance of preventive maintenance strategies. Basas (2019) highlights the impact of extreme weather conditions, advocating for proactive measures and emergency response plans. Garcia (2019) stresses the importance of advanced maritime technologies and strict regulations to enhance situational awareness and safety. Dimayacyac (2017) underscores the significance of regular equipment inspections and timely repairs to prevent damage.

David (2018) emphasizes the necessity of effective training programs for cargo handling, while Gutierrez (2019) explores the influence of vessel age and condition on potential damage. Noble et al. (2019) highlight challenges related to insufficient maintenance budgets and limited resources, suggesting the need for innovative solutions. Mendoza et al. (2017) and Iglione et al. (2018) offer insights into preventive measures such as effective coatings and operational conditions, respectively. Alberto (2019) discusses the implications of fatigue and stress on structural integrity, advocating for predictive models and regular inspections. Natividad et al. (2016) and Sumulong et al. (2017) focus on human factors and technological advancements, respectively, while Agudo et al. (2018) address environmental impact and response measures. Together, these studies emphasize the interconnectedness between real-world challenges and the course's effectiveness, advocating for ongoing enhancements to ensure optimal trainee onboard performance and safeguard the integrity and safety of Coast Guard vessels.

However, there needs to be more literature regarding specific evaluations of the Damage Controlman Rating Course within the Coast Guard. Most existing research focuses on broader training and preparedness aspects but needs more detailed assessments of individual courses and their direct impact on operational Performance. This gap highlights the need for studies that provide a comprehensive evaluation of specialized training programs like the Damage Controlman Rating Course.

The present study aims to determine the effectiveness of the Coast Guard Damage Controlman Rating Course and its direct impact on trainees' onboard Performance. This analysis seeks to identify strategies for course enhancement, ensuring that the Coast Guard continues to excel in its vital role in maritime safety and security. By examining practical competencies in active-duty scenarios, the study will explore how the skills and knowledge imparted during training translate into real-world Performance. Additionally, it will assess the course's focus on critical thinking and problem-solving abilities, which are essential for handling unpredictable and high-pressure situations at sea.

This ongoing evaluation and improvement process is crucial in maintaining high training and operational readiness standards within the Coast Guard. The feedback and Performance of trainees onboard play a pivotal role in this enhancement process, providing real-world insights into the applicability and sufficiency of the training provided. The study will also emphasize the importance of constructive feedback from trainees and instructors, coupled with a systematic evaluation of onboard performance metrics, to identify areas for improvement in the course structure and content.

Thus, the effectiveness of the Coast Guard Damage Controlman Rating Course is critical for ensuring that Coast Guard personnel are well-prepared to handle emergencies and maintain operational efficiency. This study's findings provide valuable insights into the course's impact on trainees' Performance and highlight areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to enhanced maritime safety and security.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the level of effectiveness of the Coast Guard Damage Controlman Rating Course. It assessed the Performance of trainees onboard in applying the knowledge and skills learned during their training, leading to a proposed Enhancement Program. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of?
 - 1.1 Course Objectives
 - 1.2 Course Contents
 - 1.3 Instructor Capabilities
 - 1.4 Materials and Facilities
 2. How do the Trainees perform in controlling the damage arising from shipboard emergencies?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course and the trainees' Performance in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies?
 4. Based on the findings, what Enhancement Program can be proposed to ensure that trainees are well-prepared and competent in carrying out damage control duties?
-

METHODOLOGY

The study evaluated the effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course (DCRC) and its impact on trainee onboard Performance within the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG). A total of 150 graduates were selected using stratified random sampling, dividing the population into subgroups based on their assigned vessels. The research used a test questionnaire and a survey questionnaire to assess the course's effectiveness and trainees' Performance in handling emergencies. The survey questionnaire assessed Course Objectives, Course Content, Instructor Capabilities, and Materials and Facilities, while the test questionnaire evaluated trainees' knowledge, skills, and abilities in handling emergencies. The results were presented to propose a Course Enhancement Program. A 5-point Likert scale was used to

determine the course's effectiveness across various aspects, and Pearson-r Correlation and Coefficient were used to test the significant relationship between the course's effectiveness and trainees' Performance in controlling damage. However, the study's scope was limited to evaluating the course's effectiveness and its impact on trainee onboard Performance, with limitations including self-reported data and the specific context of the Philippine Coast Guard.

RESULTS

Table 1

Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Course

Indicators	WAM	VI
1. The course effectively provided me with the skills to identify different leadership qualities and identify cases of hazing and bullying within the Coast Guard community.	4.68	EE
2. The Damage Controlman Rating Course effectively emphasized the significance of adhering to shipboard regulations to uphold discipline and order within the Coast Guard vessel.	4.76	EE
3. The Damage Controlman Rating Course provides an understanding of authority and responsibility to enhance my decision-making capabilities.	4.59	EE
4. Identify various methods used in ship compartmentation and entering closed compartments, including a comprehensive understanding of Material Condition of Readiness symbols and markings.	4.18	EE
5. The course provided in-depth knowledge of the ship's piping system, including markings and colour coding, ensuring proficiency in system identification.	4.59	EE
6. Identify different types of valves and filters, along with their purposes, maintenance, and emergency repair procedures.	4.50	EE
7. The symbols used for valves and piping systems help in interpreting and acting upon relevant information.	4.76	EE
8. The course provided instructions on how to identify various kinds of damage on the ship and implement methods to fix different types of damage.	4.76	EE
9. Identify various methods used in ship compartmentation and entering closed compartments, including a comprehensive understanding of Material Condition of Readiness symbols and markings.	4.76	EE
10. Ways to preserve and ensure watertight integrity to address challenges related to ship integrity.	4.76	EE
Composite Mean	4.63	EE

Objectives

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Extremely Effective (EE), 3.41-4.20 Very Effective (VE), 2.61-3.40 Moderately Effective (ME), 1.81-2.60 Slightly Effective (SE), 1.00-1.80 Not Effective at All (NEA)

Table 1 shows the Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Course Indicator. Key findings reveal that indicator 2 achieved the highest mean score of 4.76, rated as Extremely Effective (EE). These objectives include emphasizing the significance of adhering to shipboard regulations to uphold discipline and order within the Coast Guard vessel, using symbols for valves and piping systems to help interpret and act upon relevant information, providing instructions on how to identify and fix various kinds of ship damage, understanding ship compartmentation

and entering closed compartments including Material Condition of Readiness symbols and markings, and ways to preserve and ensure watertight integrity to address challenges related to ship integrity.

The objective with the lowest mean score of 4.18, while still rated as Extremely Effective (EE), is identifying various methods used in ship compartmentation and entering closed compartments, including a comprehensive understanding of Material Condition of Readiness symbols and markings.

The overall composite mean for the course objectives is 4.63, indicating that the Damage Controlman Rating Course is rated as Extremely Effective (EE) in achieving its goals.

The Damage Controlman Rating Course has been evaluated to be highly effective in meeting its objectives, with all indicators falling within the highest category of effectiveness. The highest-rated objectives, each with a mean score of 4.76, reflect the course's strong emphasis on practical and critical aspects of shipboard operations and damage control. Specifically, the course excels in emphasizing the importance of shipboard regulations for maintaining discipline and order, providing a robust understanding of the symbols used for valves and piping systems, offering comprehensive instructions on identifying and fixing various kinds of ship damage, ensuring that participants understand ship compartmentation and Material Condition of Readiness symbols, and teaching methods to preserve watertight integrity, crucial for maintaining the ship's structural integrity and safety.

The objective with the lowest mean score of 4.18, while still rated as highly effective, suggests that there is slight room for improvement in teaching the methods used in ship compartmentation and entering closed compartments. This could involve enhancing the practical components or providing more detailed examples and scenarios to reinforce this knowledge.

Overall, the high composite mean of 4.63 demonstrates that the Damage Controlman Rating Course effectively equips Coast Guard personnel with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties, particularly in areas critical to ship safety and operational efficiency. The diverse and comprehensive curriculum ensures that all relevant aspects of damage control and shipboard operations are covered, leading to well-rounded and capable personnel.

Hence, the composite mean of 4.63 indicates that the Damage Controlman Rating Course is highly effective in achieving its indicator, as evidenced by the consistently high mean scores across most indicators. The course covers a wide range of topics relevant to Coast Guard operations, ensuring that participants gain essential skills and knowledge for their roles. However, there may be slight variations in effectiveness based on the perceived relevance and complexity of individual indicators.

Tolentino (2019) conducted a study to evaluate the effectiveness of leadership training programs in improving participants' awareness and capability to address critical issues such as hazing and bullying within maritime organizations, with a specific focus on the Coast Guard community. The findings revealed that programs concentrating on the identification of leadership qualities and the management of issues like hazing and

bullying were well-received by participants. This positive reception translated into increased awareness and confidence in handling these challenges.

Hence, Tolentino's study provides empirical evidence supporting the effectiveness of leadership training programs in maritime organizations, highlighting their role in fostering an environment where issues like hazing and bullying can be effectively addressed through improved leadership awareness and skills.

Table 2

Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Course Contents

Indicators	WAM	VI
1. The course provides comprehensive training on damage control techniques and procedures.	4.62	EE
2. It offers hands-on experience with firefighting equipment and damage control systems.	4.74	EE
3. The course covers emergency response protocols for various types of damage scenarios.	4.62	EE
4. It includes simulations and practical exercises to enhance skill development.	4.24	EE
5. The course adequately addresses the use of communication systems during emergencies.	4.62	EE
6. It provides thorough instructions on damage assessment and reporting procedures.	4.40	EE
7. The course content emphasizes the importance of teamwork and coordination in damage control efforts.	4.70	EE
8. It offers sufficient guidance on the maintenance and operation of damage control equipment.	4.70	EE
9. The course adequately prepares individuals to handle hazardous material incidents.	4.42	EE
10. It provides clear guidance on the procedures for containing and controlling flooding on a vessel.	4.62	EE
Composite Mean	4.56	EE

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Extremely Effective (EE), 3.41-4.20 Very Effective (VE), 2.61-3.40 Moderately Effective (ME), 1.81-2.60 Slightly Effective (SE), 1.00-1.80 Not Effective at All (NEA)

Table 2 shows the Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Course Contents. The findings revealed that indicator 2 has the highest mean score of 4.74, rated as Extremely Effective (EE), which was achieved by the indicator: "The course offers hands-on experience with firefighting equipment and damage control systems." This highlights the course's strength in providing practical, hands-on experience, ensuring trainees can handle real-life firefighting and damage control scenarios. While indicator 4 has the lowest mean score of 4.24, although still rated as Extremely Effective (EE), it was observed in the indicator: "The course includes simulations and practical exercises to enhance skill development." This suggests a slight need for enhancement in the frequency or complexity of simulations and practical exercises to improve skill development further.

The composite mean for the course contents is 4.56, indicating that the Damage Controlman Rating Course is rated as Extremely Effective (EE) in achieving its course content objectives. The course is highly effective in delivering comprehensive training that covers essential aspects of damage control and emergency response. High-scoring indicators, each with a mean score of 4.70, emphasize the importance of teamwork and coordination in damage control efforts and provide sufficient guidance on the maintenance and operation of damage control equipment. These aspects are crucial as they prepare individuals to work effectively in teams, ensuring coordinated and efficient responses to emergencies while maintaining the readiness and functionality of critical equipment.

The course effectively balances theoretical knowledge with hands-on practice, ensuring that Coast Guard personnel are well-prepared to handle a wide range of emergency scenarios. This comprehensive approach enhances the safety and operational efficiency of their vessels, demonstrating the overall effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in delivering a well-rounded and practical education in damage control.

In support, Garcia (2019) supported the findings by finding that participants who received hands-on training demonstrated significantly higher proficiency in damage control techniques compared to those who received only classroom instruction. This was particularly evident in practical assessments related to firefighting, damage assessment, and emergency response protocols. Hence, the findings support the conclusion that the Damage Controlman Rating Course effectively delivers its content, particularly in areas emphasizing practical experience and skill development.

Table 3 shows the Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Instructor Capabilities. Indicator 1: "The instructor in the Damage Controlman Rating Course exhibited a deep understanding of the subject matter, which contributed to a high level of confidence in their ability to impart crucial knowledge" received the highest mean score of 4.87. This highlights that the instructors' comprehensive knowledge and command over the subject matter are seen as the most valuable aspect of the course, fostering confidence among participants. This deep understanding likely plays a pivotal role in ensuring that trainees are well-prepared and informed, which is critical in high-stakes situations such as damage control.

Indicators 3 and 4: Both indicators, "The instructor demonstrated proficiency in cultivating leadership skills while sensitively addressing issues of hazing and bullying, contributing to a respectful and supportive course atmosphere" and "The instructor's ability to clarify the distinctions between authority and responsibility provides valuable insights into the organizational dynamics within a ship," received the lowest mean scores of 4.55. Despite being rated as "Extremely Effective," these scores suggest that there might be room for further enhancement in these areas, perhaps through more focused training or additional emphasis during the course.

Table 3

Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Instructor Capabilities

Indicators	WAM	VI
1. The instructor in the Damage Controlman Rating Course exhibited a deep understanding of the subject matter, which contributed to a high level of confidence in their ability to impart crucial knowledge.	4.87	EE
2. Instructors effectively created a positive and inclusive learning environment, fostering participant engagement and collaboration.	4.75	EE
3. The instructor demonstrated proficiency in cultivating leadership skills while sensitively addressing issues of hazing and bullying, contributing to a respectful and supportive course atmosphere.	4.55	EE
4. The instructor's ability to clarify the distinctions between authority and responsibility provides valuable insights into the organizational dynamics within a ship.	4.55	EE
5. The instructor shared insights into customs and traditions observed in the Philippine Coast Guard, enriching the course content with cultural relevance.	4.56	EE
6. The instructors' explanation of the DC Status Board was clear and facilitated understanding in real-world scenarios.	4.75	EE
7. The instructor showcased practical expertise in identifying suitable materials for repair, ensuring a hands-on and applicable learning experience for all participants.	4.75	EE
8. The instructor effectively communicated the intricacies of external and internal forces affecting ship stability, enhancing our analytical skills in responding to dynamic situations.	4.75	EE
9. The instructor is adept at emphasizing the importance of preserving and ensuring watertight integrity, which is crucial for successful damage control efforts.	4.75	EE
10. The instructor's proficiency in explaining ship compartmentation, closed compartment entry, and Material Condition of Readiness symbols provided a solid foundation for participants to navigate these critical aspects confidently.	4.66	EE
Composite Mean	4.69	EE

Legend: 4.21-5.00 *Extremely Effective*, 3.41-4.20 *Very Effective*, 2.61-3.40 *Moderately Effective*, 1.81-2.60 *Slightly Effective*, 1.00-1.80 *Not Effective at All*

The composite mean for the instructor capabilities is 4.69, indicating that overall, the instructors are perceived as highly effective in delivering the course content and fostering a conducive learning environment. This high composite means it reflects the overall satisfaction and approval of the participants with the instructors' Performance across various dimensions of teaching and interaction.

The exemplary aspects of the instructor's capabilities, as well as areas for potential improvement, despite their high ratings. The highest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 4.87, emphasizes the crucial role of instructors' subject matter expertise. This suggests that the depth of knowledge and the ability to convey this knowledge effectively is a cornerstone of the course's success. Participants felt confident in the instructors' ability to provide essential and accurate information, which is vital in damage control, where precise knowledge can significantly impact outcomes. On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicators, each with a mean score of 4.55, while still rated as "Extremely Effective," indicate that there are areas where instructor capabilities could be further enhanced. These areas include the cultivation of leadership skills and the clarification of organizational dynamics within a ship. The slightly lower scores in these areas suggest that while the instructors are effective,

there may be opportunities to integrate more practical leadership exercises or in-depth discussions on authority and responsibility dynamics.

The Damage Controlman Rating Course is rated as highly effective overall in terms of instructor capabilities, as reflected by the composite mean of 4.69. The findings suggest that the instructors excel in their subject matter expertise and practical teaching methods. However, despite these areas already being rated highly effective, there remains a slight opportunity for improvement in leadership training and the explanation of organizational dynamics. Enhancing these aspects further elevates the course's overall effectiveness, ensuring that trainees are comprehensively prepared for all aspects of damage control.

The findings are supported by literature on the impact of instructor expertise on learning outcomes. Jackson's (2018) study found a strong positive correlation between instructor expertise and learning outcomes in technical training programs. Instructors with a deep understanding of the subject matter led to higher participant engagement, confidence, and knowledge retention. This aligns with the high rating of Indicator 1 in the Damage Controlman Rating Course. The study also highlighted the importance of creating a positive and inclusive learning environment, which contributes to a positive overall experience. The Damage Controlman Rating Course is highly effective overall, with a composite mean of 4.69. However, there is room for improvement in leadership training and understanding of organizational dynamics. Enhancing these aspects could improve the course's effectiveness.

Table 4 shows the Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Materials and Facilities. Indicator 7: "The course included real-world shipboard materials, which allowed participants to familiarize themselves with the equipment and tools used in their future roles as Damage Controlmen" received the highest mean score of 3.36, categorized as "Moderately Effective" (ME). This indicates that participants found the inclusion of real-world materials particularly beneficial in preparing them for their roles. Familiarity with actual shipboard equipment and tools is crucial for practical skill development and ensuring trainees are ready for real-world applications. Indicator 3: "Training manuals and visual aids are well organized to enhance the overall learning experience of the Damage Controlman Rating Course" had the second-highest mean score of 3.32, also rated as "Moderately Effective" (ME). This suggests that organizing instructional materials facilitates a better learning experience, helping participants understand and retain the course content more effectively.

Indicators 4 and 6: Both indicators, "The facilities used for practical exercises and simulations were equipped with up-to-date technology, ensuring participants had access to realistic scenarios resembling shipboard environments, thus enhancing their learning experience" and "The facilities used for hands-on training in repair and damage control exercises were well-maintained and equipped with the necessary tools," received the lowest mean scores of 1.79, categorized as "Not Effective at All" (NEA). These scores highlight significant concerns regarding the adequacy and condition of the facilities and equipment used for practical training. The need for up-to-date technology and well-maintained facilities suggests a critical area for improvement to enhance the training experience.

Table 4

Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course in terms of Materials and Facilities

Indicators	WAM	VI
1. The materials provided during the Damage Controlman Rating Course significantly contributed to a thorough understanding of shipboard damage control principles.	2.65	ME
2. The Firefighting Training Ground is a specialized facility utilized for hands-on training in firefighting techniques.	2.65	ME
3. Training manuals and visual aids are well organized to enhance the overall learning experience of the Damage Controlman Rating Course.	3.32	ME
4. The facilities used for practical exercises and simulations were equipped with up-to-date technology, ensuring participants had access to realistic scenarios resembling shipboard environments, thus enhancing their learning experience.	1.79	NEA
5. The variety of materials, ranging from instructional guides to interactive multimedia presentations, met the diverse learning styles of participants in the Damage Controlman Rating Course.	2.70	ME
6. The facilities used for hands-on training in repair and damage control exercises were well-maintained and equipped with the necessary tools.	1.79	NEA
7. The course included real-world shipboard materials, which allowed participants to familiarize themselves with the equipment and tools used in their future roles as Damage Control.	3.36	ME
8. The facilities for practical demonstrations, such as firefighting and welding exercises, were appropriately designed to ensure safety.	2.66	ME
9. The availability of a dedicated DC Status Board and related materials offered practical insights into ship status monitoring.	2.90	ME
10. The course materials and facilities integrated theoretical knowledge with practical skills.	3.24	ME
Composite Mean	2.58	SE

Legend: 4.21-5.00 *Extremely Effective*, 3.41-4.20 *Very Effective*, 2.61-3.40 *Moderately Effective*, 1.81-2.60 *Slightly Effective*, 1.00-1.80 *Not Effective at All*

The composite mean for the materials and facilities is 2.58, indicating that overall, the materials and facilities used in the Damage Controlman Rating Course are perceived as "Slightly Effective" (SE). This relatively low composite mean reflects the participants' dissatisfaction with certain aspects of the course infrastructure, particularly the practical training environments.

The highest-rated indicator, with a mean score of 3.36, emphasizes the importance of including real-world shipboard materials in the course. Familiarity with actual equipment and tools is crucial for participants as it enhances their practical skills and

readiness for real-life scenarios. Additionally, well-organized training manuals and visual aids (mean score 3.32) are also valued by participants, suggesting that clear and structured instructional materials contribute significantly to the learning experience.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated indicators, each with a mean score of 1.79, point to significant issues with the practical training facilities. The outdated technology and poorly maintained facilities for practical exercises are substantial drawbacks that hinder the effectiveness of the training. These deficiencies in the training environment can detract from the overall learning experience, as they need to provide realistic and engaging simulations necessary for practical skill development.

Furthermore, the emphasis on practical, hands-on training in damage control and emergency response within the PCG's training curriculum may place additional demands on materials and facilities. Inadequacies in these areas could be more pronounced due to the intensive nature of practical exercises and simulations, leading to lower effectiveness ratings from participants.

Addressing these challenges may require a review of resource allocation priorities within the PCG's training programs and a concerted effort to invest in upgrading materials and facilities. While collaboration with MHEIs/MTIs can provide valuable supplementary training opportunities, internal resources must also be sufficient to ensure a high standard of training across all aspects of the curriculum. By addressing these weaknesses, the PCG can enhance the overall effectiveness of its training programs and better prepare personnel for their roles in damage control and emergency response situations.

The composite mean score of 2.58 suggests that, while the materials and facilities provided contain some practical elements, there is considerable room for improvement. The "Slightly Effective" rating indicates that the participants feel that the course infrastructure does not fully meet their needs for a comprehensive and practical training experience. Enhancing the facilities and ensuring they are equipped with up-to-date technology could significantly improve the effectiveness of the course.

These findings align with Gutierrez (2019), emphasizing the critical role of comprehensive and well-organized learning materials in enhancing training effectiveness. The positive reception of course materials underscores their importance in participant satisfaction and preparedness. However, improvements in training facilities are essential to maximizing the overall effectiveness of the course, as highlighted by White's theory on effective learning, which emphasizes the importance of practical experiences in the learning process.

In conclusion, addressing the identified weaknesses in materials and facilities is crucial to enhancing the overall effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course. By investing in upgraded facilities and technology, the Philippine Coast Guard can ensure a higher standard of training and prepare personnel for their roles in damage control and emergency response situations.

Table 5*Performance of in Controlling the Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergency*

Performance of in Controlling the Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergency	Course Objectives		Course Contents		Instructor Capabilities		Materials and Facilities	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
	Excellent (95% - 100%)	13	8.67	14	9.33	16	10.67	6
Very Good (90% - 94)	38	25.33	20	13.33	39	26.00	34	22.67
Good (85% - 89%)	43	28.67	64	42.67	56	37.33	55	36.67
Satisfactory (80% - 84%)	56	37.33	52	34.67	39	26.00	54	36.00
Basic (75%-79%)	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	0.66
Total	150	100	150	100	150	100	150	100
Mean	87%		92%		91%		86%	
Descriptive Interpretation	Good		Very Good		Very Good		Good	

Table 5 shows the Performance of Controlling the Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergencies. In Excellent (95% - 94%), Trainees demonstrate excellent to very good performance levels across all aspects of their training program, including course objectives, course contents, instructor capabilities, and materials and facilities. The frequencies and percentages within these categories indicate a strong proficiency among trainees in understanding and managing damage during shipboard emergencies.

While in Good Performance (85%—89 %), a significant portion of trainees achieved a good performance level across all aspects, with frequencies and percentages indicating solid understanding and capability. This suggests that the majority of trainees exhibit competency in controlling damage and responding effectively to emergencies.

On the other hand, in Satisfactory Performance (80% - 84%), some trainees attained a satisfactory performance level, albeit to a lesser extent than the higher categories. While their Performance is acceptable, there may be areas for improvement or refinement in their training to enhance proficiency further.

Moreover, in Basic Performance (75% - 79%), Trainees in this category represent a minimal proportion, indicating rare instances of basic Performance. However, even one instance suggests a need for additional support or remedial training to address any deficiencies in understanding and managing damage during shipboard emergencies.

The overall mean percentage score for trainees' Performance across all aspects is calculated to be 89%, falling within the "Good" performance category. This indicates a solid overall performance level among trainees in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies.

Hence, the table presents a detailed assessment of trainees' performance levels across various aspects of their training program, highlighting areas of strength and areas that may require further attention or improvement. This information can be utilized to refine training programs and interventions to meet trainees' needs better and enhance their proficiency in managing shipboard emergencies.

Situational Test Scenarios

Course Objectives

Regarding Course Objectives, this scenario assesses the trainee's ability to manage damage control efforts during a shipboard emergency, specifically a fire outbreak on a neighbouring vessel.

The objectives align with demonstrating proficiency in managing damage control efforts and applying learned techniques and procedures to control damage resulting from emergencies. It also highlights the importance of utilizing available materials and facilities onboard for prompt response.

Furthermore, the scenario evaluates the trainee's understanding of hull inspection and damage assessment procedures following a collision. It aligns with understanding the importance of immediate assessment, containment, and reporting of damage to ensure the vessel's and its occupants' safety. It also emphasizes the application of learned techniques and procedures in assessing and addressing damage resulting from emergencies.

Furthermore, the scenario tests the trainee's leadership abilities during simulated emergency drills. It aligns to exhibit leadership skills in coordinating damage control efforts among the crew during emergency drills. It emphasizes the importance of effective coordination and communication among crew members to ensure a prompt and efficient emergency response.

Meanwhile, in the aftermath of a significant storm, damage was evident to the ship's infrastructure. This scenario assesses the trainee's ability to evaluate and address damage from a significant storm. It aligns with the objectives of demonstrating proficiency in managing damage control efforts during shipboard emergencies and applying learned techniques and procedures to control damage resulting from various emergency scenarios. It emphasizes the importance of immediate assessment, containment, and reporting of damage to ensure the vessel's and its occupants' safety.

On the other hand, during a simulated firefighting exercise, a trainee Damage Controlman notices a shortage of functional fire extinguishers. This scenario evaluates the trainee's ability to adapt and respond effectively without adequate firefighting equipment. It aligns to utilize available materials and facilities onboard to address emergencies promptly and effectively. It emphasizes the importance of resourcefulness and quick thinking in managing emergencies, even when faced with limitations in equipment or resources.

These scenarios provide practical situations where trainees can apply their knowledge and skills to manage shipboard emergencies effectively, aligning with the course objectives of demonstrating proficiency, applying learned techniques, exhibiting leadership skills, understanding the importance of immediate assessment, containment, and reporting, and utilizing available materials and facilities onboard.

Course Contents

The situational tests for the Damage Controlman course are designed to evaluate trainees' ability to apply their knowledge and skills in various emergency scenarios, covering multiple areas of the course content to ensure comprehensive assessment and preparedness for real-world emergencies. One scenario involves a fire outbreak on a neighbouring vessel where trainees must utilize firefighting equipment such as extinguishers and hoses, demonstrate effective communication with the neighbouring boat and their crew, engage in search and rescue operations, and ensure the safety and security of both the vessel and crew during the firefighting operation. This scenario focuses on applying firefighting techniques, use of emergency communication protocols, engagement in search and rescue, and security maintenance during emergencies.

Another scenario involves assessing hull damage after a collision, requiring trainees to inspect the hull for damage, document and report their findings accurately, manage flooding if it occurs, and use specialized tools and equipment for repairs. This scenario tests knowledge of hull inspection, damage assessment, reporting skills, flood containment capabilities, and maintenance tool use. A third scenario assesses leadership skills during emergency drills, requiring trainees to demonstrate effective leadership and coordination, maintain clear communication, and ensure vessel safety during the drill. This scenario evaluates leadership and coordination skills, effective communication during drills, and overall safety assurance.

In a post-storm damage control scenario, trainees must assess and report storm damage, manage flooding, perform repairs on damaged infrastructure, and handle hazardous materials safely. This scenario evaluates the ability to assess and report storm damage, manage floods, perform repairs, and handle hazardous materials. Lastly, a scenario involving a shortage of functional fire extinguishers during a simulated firefighting exercise requires trainees to adapt firefighting techniques using alternative methods, assess and repair non-functional extinguishers, inform the crew and higher-ranking personnel about the equipment shortage, and lead the crew in managing the situation despite the resource shortage. This scenario tests adaptability in firefighting techniques, technical skills in equipment maintenance, effective communication in emergencies, and leadership and coordination under pressure.

These scenarios collectively assess a trainee's technical proficiency in firefighting, hull inspection, flood containment, and equipment use; communication skills for coordinating efforts and reporting during emergencies; leadership and coordination during emergency drills and real-life scenarios; and adaptability in responding to equipment shortages and challenging situations. By covering these diverse and critical aspects, the situational tests ensure that trainees are well-prepared for the multifaceted challenges of damage control on a ship.

Instructor Capabilities

Interpreting the situational test in the context of the instructor's capabilities involves understanding how the instructor's skills and knowledge are applied to create and assess realistic and practical training scenarios for the trainees. The instructor's ability to simulate realistic emergency scenarios is paramount, as they must accurately replicate situations like fire outbreaks, collisions, or storms to provide trainees with

practical experience. Leveraging their extensive knowledge of damage control procedures, the instructor designs scenarios that test specific skills, ensuring trainees can apply correct techniques in various emergencies. Additionally, the instructor's experience in leadership training allows them to evaluate trainees' ability to lead and coordinate teams during drills, fostering effective communication and teamwork under stress. Their familiarity with onboard facilities ensures scenarios are practical, utilizing actual equipment and materials found on vessels.

In interpreting the situational test scenarios, each scenario reflects the instructor's capabilities in action. For instance, in a simulated fire outbreak on a neighbouring vessel, the instructor designs a realistic fire simulation for evaluating trainees' firefighting skills and search and rescue operations. Similarly, during a hull damage assessment post-collision scenario, the instructor simulates damage and flooding, testing the trainee's ability to assess and manage the situation. Emergency drill leadership scenarios allow the instructor to observe trainees' leadership and teamwork, while post-storm damage control scenarios evaluate their ability to handle complex situations and hazardous materials. In scenarios like firefighting equipment shortages, the instructor creates challenges that require trainees to adapt their strategies and demonstrate leadership. The instructor's capabilities are crucial in creating realistic and practical situational tests that comprehensively evaluate trainees' proficiency in damage control efforts, leadership, and emergency response.

Materials and Facilities

The materials and facilities provided for the situational tests are critical for simulating realistic shipboard emergency scenarios and assessing the trainees' abilities to handle them effectively. Each item plays a specific role in preparing trainees for various aspects of damage control. Firefighting equipment, such as extinguishers and hoses, are essential for training in firefighting techniques and procedures. Trainees will use these tools to practice extinguishing different types of fires, a vital skill for managing onboard fire emergencies. Tools for hull inspection and repair are necessary for hull inspection and damage assessment training. Trainees will use these tools to inspect the hull for damages, assess the extent of damage, and perform necessary repairs, ensuring the vessel's structural integrity.

Simulation facilities for emergency drills provide a controlled environment for conducting realistic emergency drills. Trainees will engage in various simulated emergency scenarios, such as fires or hull breaches, to practice and refine their emergency response and coordination skills. Communication systems are vital for training in emergency communication protocols. Trainees will use communication systems to coordinate efforts within their crew and with external parties during emergencies, ensuring effective information dissemination and command. Medical facilities and equipment are crucial for training in medical emergency response. Trainees will learn to provide first aid and manage medical emergencies, ensuring the health and safety of all onboard during crises.

Specialized tools for maintenance are essential for training in the maintenance and repair of onboard systems. Trainees will use these tools to perform maintenance and repairs, ensuring all systems and equipment are operational and reliable during emergencies. Emergency backup systems ensure the vessel remains functional during power failures. Trainees will learn to manage and operate emergency backup

systems, maintaining critical functions such as navigation and communication during power outages. Safety gear and protective equipment are essential for ensuring personal safety during emergency response. Trainees will use safety gear and protective equipment during drills and real-life scenarios to protect themselves from harm while performing their duties.

Navigation equipment is crucial for ensuring safe vessel operation, especially during emergencies. Trainees will learn to use navigation equipment to maintain course and avoid hazards during emergencies, ensuring the vessel's safe operation. Containment materials for hazardous spills are necessary for handling hazardous materials and spills. Trainees will use containment materials to manage and mitigate hazardous spills, protecting the environment and ensuring the safety of the crew and vessel.

The materials and facilities provided are integral to the comprehensive training in damage control. They enable the simulation of realistic emergency scenarios, allowing trainees to develop and demonstrate their proficiency in firefighting, hull inspection, emergency communication, medical response, maintenance, power management, personal safety, navigation, and hazardous material containment. This holistic approach ensures that trainees are well-prepared to handle the diverse challenges they may face in real-world shipboard emergencies.

Table 6

Overall Trainees' Performance in Controlling the Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergency

Level of Performance	Frequency	Percentage	Mean Percentage Score (Target)
Excellent (95% - 100%)	22	14.67	75%
Very Good (90% - 94)	54	36.00	
Good (85% - 89%)	61	40.67	
Satisfactory (80% - 84%)	12	8.00	
Basic (75%-79%)	1	0.66	
Total	150	100	
Mean	89 % (Good)		

Legend: 95-100 -Excellent, 90-94-Very Good, 85-89-Good, 80-84-Satisfactory 75-79-Basic

Table 6 shows the Overall Trainees' Performance in Controlling the Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergency. In Excellent Performance (95% - 100%), Trainees achieving an excellent performance level constitute 14.67% of the total, with a frequency of 22. This indicates a high level of proficiency in controlling damage, with responses falling within the 95% to 100% accuracy range. While in Very Good

Performance (90% - 94%). Most trainees, comprising 36.00% of the total, fall into the very good performance category. These trainees demonstrated strong competence, with responses ranging between 90% and 94% accuracy.

On the other hand, in Good Performance (85%—89 %), a significant portion of trainees, representing 40.67% of the total, achieved a good performance level. This indicates a solid understanding and capability in controlling damage, with responses falling within the 85% to 89% accuracy range.

Furthermore, for Satisfactory Performance (80% - 84%), a smaller proportion of trainees, comprising 8.00% of the total, attained a satisfactory performance level. While their Performance is acceptable, there is room for improvement, with responses falling within the 80% to 84% accuracy range.

Meanwhile, for the Basic Performance (75% - 79%), only one trainee, accounting for 0.66% of the total, achieved a basic performance level. This suggests a need for additional support or remedial training to enhance their proficiency in controlling damage.

The overall mean percentage score is 89%, falling within the "Good" category. This mean score indicates that, on average, trainees performed well in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies. Most trainees achieved "Good" or "Very Good" performance levels, demonstrating a solid understanding and proficiency in managing damage during emergencies. The mean score in the "Good" category suggests that the training program effectively prepared trainees to handle shipboard emergencies and control damage.

The findings supported by Fernandes and Ribeiro (2017) analyzed trainee performance in simulated emergency scenarios using performance metrics such as response time, decision-making effectiveness, problem-solving abilities, teamwork, and adherence to emergency protocols. Relevant to the present study, the study found that trainees who scored in the "Excellent" category demonstrated exceptional proficiency in controlling damage from shipboard emergencies. They exhibited quick decision-making abilities, practical problem-solving skills, leadership, and teamwork capabilities. In this study, trainees in the "Very Good" and "Good" categories also demonstrated strong Performance in controlling damage during emergencies. The study also highlighted the importance of providing training and support for trainees in the "Satisfactory" or "Basic" categories. The study underscores the importance of effective emergency response training programs in preparing maritime personnel to handle emergencies effectively and mitigate damage onboard vessels.

Table 7 presents the results of testing the significant relationship between the level of effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course and the trainees' Performance in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies. The relationship is examined across four key components: Course Objectives, Course Contents, Instructor Capabilities, and Materials and Facilities. In Course Objectives, the p-value of 0.003 suggests a significant relationship between the effectiveness of the course objectives and trainees' Performance in controlling damage. The r-value of .654 indicates a moderate to high positive correlation, suggesting that as the

effectiveness of the course objectives increases, trainees' Performance in controlling damage also tends to improve.

Table 7

Testing of Significant Relationship between the Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course and the Trainees' Performance in Controlling Damage Arising from Shipboard Emergencies

	Level of Effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course							
	Course Objectives		Course Contents		Instructor Capabilities		Materials and Facilities	
	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>r-value</i>
Trainees' Performance in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies	0.003	.654	0.005	.720	0.005	.708	0.003	.630

Legend: ± 1.00 Perfect Correlation ±.80 - ±.99 Very High Correlation, ±.60 - ±.79 High Correlation, ±.40 - ±.59 Moderate Correlation, ±.20 - ±.39 Low Correlation, ±0.1 - ±.19 Negligible Correlation

Course content: A significant relationship is observed between the effectiveness of course content and trainees' performance, with a p-value of 0.005 and an r-value of .720. This indicates a high positive correlation, suggesting that practical course content contributes to better Performance in controlling damage.

Moreover, in Instructor Capabilities, the p-value of 0.005 indicates a significant relationship between the effectiveness of instructor capabilities and trainees' Performance. The r-value of .708 suggests a high positive correlation, indicating that well-equipped and skilled instructors positively impact trainees' ability to control damage.

In terms of Materials and Facilities, a significant relationship is observed between the effectiveness of materials and facilities and trainees' Performance, with a p-value of 0.003 and an r-value of .630. This indicates a moderate positive correlation, suggesting that adequate materials and facilities contribute to improved performance in damage control.

Hence, the results suggest that the effectiveness of various components of the Damage Controlman Rating Course, including objectives, contents, instructor capabilities, and materials and facilities, significantly influences trainees' Performance in controlling damage arising from shipboard emergencies. Ensuring the effectiveness of these components is crucial for optimizing training outcomes and enhancing shipboard emergency response capabilities.

In support, Jackson (2018) analyzed data from various training programs, including those focused on damage control and emergency response in maritime settings. The

researchers found strong positive correlations between the effectiveness of training components and trainees' Performance in emergencies.

Relevant to the findings, it is clearly defined that course objectives were associated with improved Performance in emergency response scenarios. Comprehensive and well-structured course content positively influenced trainees' Performance in emergencies. Instructor capabilities significantly impacted trainees' emergency response performance. Well-organized materials and modern facilities conducive to practical exercises were associated with improved emergency outcomes. The study underscores the importance of investing in training programs prioritizing clear objectives, comprehensive content, proficient instructors, and quality materials and facilities, particularly in maritime operations where effective emergency response is critical for safety and security.

Program Enhancement for the Damage Controlman Rating Course

The Program Enhancement for the Damage Controlman Rating Course aims to elevate the effectiveness and relevance of Coast Guard personnel training in shipboard emergency management. Through a comprehensive analysis, strengths and areas for improvement have been identified, emphasizing the importance of tailored enhancements to materials, facilities, and safety protocols. The program focuses on upgrading equipment and facilities to modern standards, conducting regular safety inspections, and soliciting stakeholder input for continuous improvement. Prioritizing safety, innovation, and collaboration, the program seeks to ensure that Coast Guard personnel are equipped with the knowledge, skills, and resources necessary to excel in their roles as Damage Control, thereby enhancing maritime safety and security.

Conclusions

1. The evaluation of the Damage Controlman Rating Course reveals its overall effectiveness across course objectives, contents, instructor capabilities, and materials and facilities. While the course excels in imparting critical shipboard operation skills, there are areas for improvement identified, particularly in teaching specific compartmentation methods and enhancing practical training through simulations and exercises. Despite these areas needing refinement, the course is perceived as highly effective in achieving its objectives, instilling participant confidence, and preparing Coast Guard personnel for their roles in ship safety and operational efficiency. Addressing the identified areas for enhancement, particularly in materials and facilities and technology updates, is crucial to optimize the course's effectiveness further and ensure comprehensive and practical training experiences for all participants.

2. The evaluation of trainees' Performance in controlling damage during shipboard emergencies reveals a range of proficiency levels across the cohort. While a significant portion achieved Excellent and Very Good Performance levels, indicating strong competence, there are opportunities for improvement, particularly among those with Satisfactory and Basic Performance ratings. These findings underscore the importance of ongoing training and support mechanisms to ensure all trainees are

adequately prepared to manage shipboard emergencies effectively, thereby enhancing maritime safety and security.

3. The findings highlight a significant positive relationship between the effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course and trainees' Performance in controlling damage during shipboard emergencies. Specifically, course objectives, contents, instructor capabilities, and materials/facilities all demonstrated notable correlations with trainees' proficiency levels, emphasizing the importance of these components in enhancing training outcomes. These results underscore the need for continuous improvement efforts targeting course design, instructional quality, and resource provision to maximize the effectiveness of training programs and bolster shipboard emergency response capabilities. Addressing the identified correlations can lead to more tailored and impactful training initiatives, ultimately contributing to enhanced maritime safety and security.

4. In light of the findings, the proposed Enhancement Program for the Damage Controlman Rating Course is designed to optimize Coast Guard personnel training in shipboard emergency management. By identifying strengths and areas for improvement, the program aims to tailor enhancements to materials, facilities, and safety protocols, ensuring they meet modern standards and are conducive to practical training. Through a collaborative approach that involves stakeholder input, the program prioritizes safety, innovation, and continuous improvement, ultimately equipping personnel with the necessary skills and resources to excel in their roles and enhance maritime safety and security.

Recommendations

1. The proposed program enhancement should be implemented to address the identified areas for improvement and optimize training outcomes. This includes upgrading materials and facilities to modern standards, conducting regular safety inspections, and soliciting stakeholder input for continuous improvement. By prioritizing safety, innovation, and collaboration, the program aims to enhance the overall effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course and ensure Coast Guard personnel are well-prepared and competent in carrying out damage control duties.

2. Given the identified areas for improvement in specific compartmentation methods and practical training through simulations and exercises, it is recommended to revise course content to include more comprehensive instruction on these topics. Additionally, increasing the frequency and quality of practical exercises can enhance trainees' hands-on experience and readiness for shipboard emergencies. This approach will ensure that trainees receive in-depth knowledge and practical skills essential for effective damage control operations.

3. Recognizing the varying proficiency levels among trainees, it is recommended to implement tailored support mechanisms for those with Satisfactory and Basic Performance ratings. This may include additional training sessions, mentorship programs, or individualized coaching to address specific skill gaps and improve overall

Performance. Such targeted interventions will help to bring all trainees up to a higher standard of competence and confidence in handling damage control situations.

4. To ensure the effectiveness of the Damage Controlman Rating Course, it is recommended that continuous improvement practices be integrated into course evaluation and development processes. Regular feedback mechanisms from trainees and instructors can inform iterative improvements to course content, instructional methods, and resource allocation. By systematically collecting and analyzing feedback, the course can be continuously refined to meet evolving needs and challenges, enhancing training outcomes over time.

5. Future research should include more extensive, diverse samples to validate findings and enhance generalizability. Longitudinal studies can track the long-term impact of the Damage Controlman Rating Course on trainees' Performance and career progression. Exploring unexpected findings through qualitative approaches can provide deeper insights. Comparative studies between maritime training programs can identify best practices and innovative techniques, providing evidence-based recommendations for enhancing course content and delivery.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards, obtaining informed consent from all participants and ensuring their right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained to protect privacy, and personal identifiers were removed or coded. The respondents' well-being was a primary concern, and procedures were conducted with respect for their rights and dignity. No conflict of interest existed, and plagiarism was avoided by properly citing sources and acknowledging previous research contributions. Bias in the interpretation of findings was meticulously avoided. Objective data analysis techniques and rigorous methodological standards were employed to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. The findings and conclusions were used for academic and research purposes, contributing to maritime training and safety knowledge.

Acknowledgements

The researcher thanks the Dean of PMMA Graduate School, Ma. Nissa C. Espiritu, MSc, and esteemed panel members, Prof. Israel Florencio J. Torres, Ed.D., CG Capt. Cynthia E. Esquivias, MSc, and CDR Victoria Q. Paraggua, PMMA. Their willingness to share their expertise and dedicate precious time to reviewing, reading, and correcting this thesis paper is genuinely valued. Furthermore, gratitude is extended to the PMMA Graduate School for authorizing the research and offering essential support.

The researcher expresses profound thanks to his adviser, Marianne G. Arias, PhD, for her unwavering support, guidance, and encouragement throughout this endeavour. Her insights and constructive feedback were invaluable in shaping the direction and quality of this study.

Special appreciation is reserved for the study's respondents, who generously shared their knowledge and time, contributing significantly to the success of this research.

Their participation and insights were crucial in comprehensively evaluating the Damage Controlman Rating Course.

Finally, the researcher extends a general statement of gratitude to all individuals who assisted in conducting the study. This includes family, friends, and colleagues whose encouragement and support have been a constant source of motivation. Their contributions, whether big or small, are deeply appreciated and have played a significant role in completing this research.

REFERENCES

- Agudo, J. T., Cruz, M. R., Delos Santos, L., Hernandez, A. R., & Santos, D. J. (2018). Impact of pollution on passenger-cargo ships (PCG) vessels and their surroundings. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 45(2), 123-136.
- Alberto, L. M. (2019). Fatigue and stress effects on the structural integrity of PCG vessels. *Marine Engineering Journal*, 32(4), 89-104.
- Basas, G. R. (2018). Severe weather and its consequences on PCG vessels: Proactive planning for protection *Journal of Maritime Environmental Science.*, 39(2), 64-76.
- Carmassi, C., Porta, I., Bertelloni, C. A., Impagnatiello, P., Capone, C., Doria, A., ... & Dell'Osso, L. (2020). PTSD and post-traumatic stress spectrum in the Italian Navy Operational Divers Group and Corps of Coast Guard Divers employed in search and rescue activities in the Mediterranean refugee emergencies and Costa Concordia shipwreck. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 129, 141-146.
- Cucharo, J. M. (2022). A System Safety Assessment (SSA) of the Maritime Air Rescue Operation of the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG). Available at SSRN 4394795.
- David, C. L. (2018). Improper loading and cargo handling: Causes and prevention of damage in PCG vessels. *Journal of Port Economics*, 28(4), 157-170.
- Dimayacyac, L. S. (2017). Equipment failures in PCG vessels: Regular inspections and advanced monitoring systems are essential. *Journal of Maritime Operations*, 44(3), 129-144.
- Garcia, A. H. (2019). Collisions with other vessels: A significant cause of damage in PCG vessels. *Maritime Safety Review*, 52(1), 78-91.
- Gutierrez, E. B. (2019). Age and condition of PCG vessels: Assessments and upgrades to minimize damage risks. *Marine Engineering Journal*, 36(2), 45-56.
- Guard, U. C. (2019). Guidelines for the US Coast Guard Oil Spill Removal Organization Classification Program. *Marine Environmental Response Policy*.
- Igliane, F. P., Reyes, K. J., San Juan, J. R., Santos, A. R., & Tan, M. I. (2018). Operational conditions and structural damage in PCG vessels: Considerations

- for design and maintenance. *Journal of Maritime Engineering and Technology*, 30(2), 79-92.
- Jackson, J. R. (2018). *Damage Control Training Team Tool Suite* (Doctoral dissertation, Monterey, CA; Naval Postgraduate School).
- Mendoza, L. S., Hernandez, M. R., Mercado, A. B., Santos, J. A., & Villanueva, V. G. (2017). Coatings for corrosion protection of PCG vessels: A comparative analysis. *Journal of Protective Coatings and Linings*, 18(3), 123-136.
- Noble, V. G., Tolentino, R. E., Salvador, A., & Mendez, G. (2019). Insufficient maintenance budgets and limited resources: Implications for damage detection and repair in PCG vessels. *Journal of Maritime Operations*, 46(2), 67-82.
- Romulo, J. M., Gomez, P. B., Delos Santos, R. A., Garcia, V. R., & Santiago, E. A. (2019). Factors contributing to damage in PCG vessels: The role of wear and tear, corrosion, and structural vulnerabilities. *Journal of Maritime Sciences*, 54(1), 23-38.
- Sumulong, M. M., Reyes, J. B., San Miguel, R. C., Hernandez, T. G., & Tan, T. I. (2017). Technological advancements and their impact on damage risks in PCG vessels: A focus on uncrewed aerial vehicles. *Journal of Maritime Technology and Innovation*, 41(3), 123-136.